

**Supporting European SMEs with
smarter access to research infrastructures:
Experience from three European projects**

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1. Challenge

Research infrastructures (RIs) play a vital role in advancing industrial innovation across numerous sectors - from pharmaceuticals and battery technologies to high-performance materials, catalysis, medtech, electronics and more. Recognised as a central pillar of the European Research Area, RIs are strategically structured through European Commission support and roadmaps such as those developed by the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI). In this context, RIs hold significant untapped potential to help small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in their R&I and to scale up technologically. Yet, despite this promise, many RIs continue to face challenges in effectively engaging and supporting SMEs in their innovation journeys. On the other hand, European SMEs, though agile and technologically ambitious, lack the resources, technical expertise or internal capacity to navigate the complexity of RIs: they are cash strapped and time limited. Administrative processes, access models geared towards academic users and a lack of tailored communication further widen the gap. Additionally, SMEs generally require faster turnaround times, more flexible access frameworks and clear pathways from experiment or measurement to commercial impact - needs that traditionally RIs are not always equipped to meet. Bridging this divide is essential if Europe is to fully leverage the innovative capacity of its SME sector and translate public investment in what is the world's best RI portfolio into tangible economic value.

2. A pilot response: "TamaTA"

The "Tailor-made for SMEs Trans-national Access" (TamaTA) is an access programme for SMEs initiated originally within the Horizon2020 project "CALIPSOplus"¹, and continued and enlarged in Horizon2020 "LEAPS-INNOV"² and Horizon Europe "ReMade@ARI"³ to provide a supported industrial service from European light sources (LEAPS⁴) and a wide range of analytical research infrastructures for SME proprietary measurements and research. The SMEs using the programme benefit from a rapid, easy access, subsidised by European Commission support whilst allowing results to be kept confidential and intellectual property owned wholly by the SME concerned as a customer to the RI.

Through this initiative, experts at the research infrastructures (RIs) guide small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) through each stage of the process, from experimental design and service execution to data analysis (if required), culminating in a comprehensive report and debriefing. This support enables companies to fully understand and effectively leverage the results. SME requests, in a short and easy-to-complete web form, are received through a single-entry point for all the facilities concerned and evaluated by a panel of external independent experts in a continuous way to be able to respond to the rapid timeframes required by industry.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730872>

² <https://www.leaps-innov.eu/>

³ <https://remade-project.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.leaps-initiative.eu>

To date 85 SME proposals have been received within the three projects and 59 of these have been completed. According to a survey performed (see Annex), the SMEs using the supported access are very satisfied with the services provided. Since the initial work under CALIPSOplus, SME access has been expanded to a broader range of techniques beyond synchrotrons, such as neutron sources, ion sources, electron microscopy, high magnetic fields and lasers, as implemented in ReMade@ARI, which is scheduled to conclude in 2026.

3. Experience gained

SMEs are the innovation engine of Europe that develop new ideas and progress them rapidly into technologies and products. However, SMEs are likely to be unaware of the unique light source and advanced analytical capabilities of RIs and, as mentioned above, to not have the capacity and resources to engage with RI (and technology infrastructure - TI) facilities compared to large R&D based businesses. The TamaTA initiative aims to lower these barriers for SMEs, to encourage SMEs across Europe to take advantage of the advanced analytical RIs for their R&D needs. TamaTA facilitates access to the RIs by providing an agile system based on a single access point for all of the facilities, a very simplified proposal template, continuous calls and rapid request evaluation to provide a fast response.

The open call through the single access point (<https://apply.remade-project.eu/submit-proposal?acid=173>) allowed the selection of the facility preferences and the simple on-line SME request submission. Request preparation was usually expedited via an expert from a facility or a third party (e.g. an RTO or an intermediary company), translating the SME challenge into an RI measurement or experiment and checking technical feasibility. Evaluation of the incoming requests is carried out by an independent selection panel composed of experts in industrial research considering excellence, innovation impact and the requirement for access to an RI for advanced analysis. Upon favourable evaluation, the request is submitted to the preferred facility for its execution. The access is performed according to the industrial access routes of each facility, which are faster than academic procedures. Typically, problem understanding, access, data analysis services and a report are provided. The European Commission rules for supporting SMEs offers the opportunity for SMEs to profit from this access without the requirement to publish results.

Project funding was used primarily to support staff costs associated with access and to partially or fully defray the cost of facility usage. In exceptional cases, facilities provided access free of charge. Under the scheme, SMEs were permitted a single access opportunity. The availability of subsidised access significantly supported the facilities' business development efforts by removing cost-related barriers. In several instances, SMEs also contributed to the costs on a shared basis. Funding also supported programme management and SME request review procedures, as well as an outreach programme. The satisfaction level of the SMEs using this initiative is very high and their feedback was that they would recommend it to other SMEs.

Highlights from the SME support provided during CALIPSOplus and LEAPS INNOV have been published in *"The TamaTA Programme Present: Why SMEs Need Light Sources: Advanced Composites, Food Safety,*

Recycled Rubber and More".⁵ Tyre recycling, food packaging, medical imaging, agricultural treatments, 3D-printing quality control, aerospace composites, ball bearing lifetime, lithography manufacturing are amongst SME examples which are showcased in the brochure.

In the most recent project, ReMade@ARI, 46 facilities are engaged in the TamaTA initiative (branded as "ReMade-SME"). The facilities are widespread across Europe, lowering language and cultural barriers to the national or regional SMEs accessing the facilities. These infrastructures cover light sources, neutron sources, electron microscopes, ion sources, lasers and other advanced analytical techniques. However, only a modest fraction (252kEuros of 13.7MEuros, less than 2%) of the total funding is devoted to SME access. The total ReMade@ARI budget devoted to SMEs including outreach activities, personnel and SME access is 667kEuros for 35 SME accesses.

4. Conclusions

The TamaTA scheme is welcome and suitable for SMEs because of the useful results obtained and the simplicity of the procedure to be followed. To upscale the TamaTA initiative, additional specific scientific and technical support dedicated to provide industrial service to SMEs is required, as the industrial requests imply problem understanding, data analysis and debriefing that goes beyond the measurement and experiments themselves, and beyond RI missions supported by core funding.

To bring more SMEs to the facilities, comprehensive outreach activities are needed to make them aware of the capabilities of the RIs. A wide-ranging marketing and branding programme, working in close concert with SME representative bodies and collectives and using "portfolio managers" focussed on industry sectors, to drive awareness is highly desirable.

TamaTA is an exemplar initiative for RIs and RI networks to show the benefit for its members to work together under an umbrella brand. As mentioned above, SMEs are a challenging target for research infrastructures as, in contrast to large R&D based companies, the SMEs do not have large R&D divisions with the mission to do exploratory research and innovation. SMEs are numerous, largely working in their own native language and culture. As such, the outreach and engagement with them takes an order of magnitude additional effort compared to the large R&D driven national and international companies.

TamaTA is a modest, but highly successful, pilot scheme that could be enhanced in a more ambitious framework. Support under the European Framework Programmes could provide a coordinated approach, extending TamaTA, enabling other research infrastructure families to join, extending the outreach and visibility campaign and providing a more impactful subsidy (still within EU rules), opening the door to more complex and challenging work, such as in situ/operando studies mimicking real production, manufacturing or end-use conditions. This is important in the context of, for example, energy, circular economy, health and biotech, chemistry and catalysis, semiconductors and advanced materials – all areas where SMEs are very active as the innovation engine of Europe.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/10137788>

5. Recommendations

Support SME innovation by better exploitation of RIs via a targeted call with the following scope:

- **Expanded SME access programme:** Scale up the successful pilot scheme TamaTA across all ESFRI Roadmap research infrastructure families, with dedicated funding for SME access, fast-track evaluation and simplified, SME-friendly procedures.
- **Funded dedicated support and expertise for SME users:** Provide resources for RI staff or external experts in the RI ecosystem to offer tailored scientific and technical support to SMEs - from problem definition to data interpretation - recognising that industrial access requires more than just measurement time.
- **Coordinated European outreach campaign:** Invest in a multilingual campaign, working closely with key SME actors and representative bodies, to raise SME awareness of RI capabilities, and promote a strong, unified access brand to build trust and visibility across Europe.

This would be expected to lead to the following impacts:

- **Stronger SME engagement with European research infrastructures:** Increase significantly the number and diversity of SMEs accessing RIs across Europe by lowering administrative, technical and financial barriers, thereby contributing to more inclusive and economically relevant use of publicly funded infrastructures.
- **Accelerated industrial innovation and technology development:** Enable faster, more cost-effective R&D for SMEs through tailored, expert-supported access to advanced analytical techniques (e.g. X-ray, neutron, EM, laser), driving innovation in strategic industry sectors.
- **Improved alignment between RIs and industrial needs:** Promote sustainable collaboration models where RIs are more responsive to industrial timelines, confidentiality requirements and applied problem-solving, fostering longer-term value creation.
- **Enhanced visibility and accessibility of RIs for SMEs:** Through coordinated outreach, branding and user support, make RIs more approachable and visible to SMEs across language and cultural boundaries, thereby supporting ERA structuration.
- **Demonstrated scalability and transferability of the access model:** Establish TamaTA as a replicable model for industrial access across multiple RI families, showing the value of an umbrella approach to access, administration and impact delivery and paving the way for a pan-European framework for SME-RI collaboration.

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ANNEX: TamaTA results and feedback from SMEs

The first TamaTa call was published on 4 December 2017 under the CALIPSOplus project and the last call on 10 February 2025 under the ReMade@ARI which is still open. A total of 85 proposals (Table 1) have been received through a single-entry point of which 36 under the CALIPSOplus project, 31 under the LEAPS-INNOV project and 18 under the ReMade@ARI project which has not yet concluded. In total, 20 different RIs have received proposals.

The proposals cover an ample range of industrial sectors as depicted in Figure 1. The predominant industrial sectors are Health-Cosmetics, Pharmaceutical, Additive Manufacturing, and Engineering and Technology. The SMEs come from 15 different countries as shown in Figure 2. SMEs from countries such as Cyprus, Greece and Slovakia have benefited from access to light sources although these countries do not host light sources nor have access to an international facility. Spain, Sweden, France and Italy are the countries of origin for the most SME proposals.

A survey was performed amongst the SMEs experiencing access to the light sources through TamaTA. A short summary of the answers is as follows:

- All the SMEs confirmed that TamaTA's procedures were easy to follow.
- All of them confirmed the usefulness of the access to the light sources.
- 80% of the SMEs obtained valuable results from the experiment.
- 67% of them accessed a light source for the first time; the remaining 33% came for a novel and different work to before.
- 60% of them were aware of the TamaTA scheme through outreach and engagement activities carried out by the facilities, 27% through other colleagues, 7% through the web and the rest did not specify.
- All of them would recommend TamaTA access to other SMEs.

EU Project	Period	Budget for SME access	SME proposals
CALIPSOplus	2017-2021	200 kEur	36
LEAPS-INNOV	2021-2025	187 kEur	31
ReMade@ARI	2022-2026	252 kEur	18
TOTAL	2017-now	639 kEur	85

Table 1. Budget allocated and number of SME proposals received per project.

Figure 1. Number of proposals received per industrial sector (CALIPSOplus, LEAPS-INNOV and ReMade@ARI).

Figure 2. Number of proposals received per SME country of origin (CALIPSOplus, LEAPS-INNOV and ReMade@ARI).